

Electrochemical screening of Lindane in natural origin, biological and industrial samples

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Abstract : Direct current polarographic method has been developed for the qualitative as well as quantitative analysis of Lindane (B.H.C.). Lindane produces a well-defined polarographic wave (DCP) in (0.1 M) tetramethyl ammonium bromide (TMAB), as supporting electrolyte (acetone used as solvent) at pH 10 ± 0.2 with $E_{1/2} = -0.995$ V vs SCE. The wave height is found to be proportional to the concentration of Lindane in solution. The developed method has been standardised for the determination of B.H.C. in vegetables, soil, fruits, blood and soft drinks. The reliability of the observed data has been tested by subjecting it to statistical treatment.

Keywords : Lindane (hexachlorocyclohexane), polarographic study.

Lindane (γ -1,2,3,4,5,6-hexachlorocyclohexane) is used to control various harmful insects, plant pests and animal parasites¹. The wide applicability and high toxicity² of the pesticide has necessitated, development of selective and sensitive methods for its determination in various samples i.e. natural origin, biological and industrial samples.

A survey of literature reveals that in order to determine Lindane at trace levels, various analytical methods³ have been used.

A polarographic method has been developed for the analysis of Lindane in samples obtained from plant products biological samples (blood) and also in soft drinks. The results of which have been reported in this paper.

Results and discussion

The direct current polarogram (DCP) of the sample solution in TMAB (0.1 M) at pH 10 ± 0.2 produced one well defined polarographic wave with $E_{1/2} = -0.995$ V vs SCE, indicating the presence of Lindane in the sample.

To confirm the presence of Lindane, a known quantity of its standard solution was added to the analyte and the polarogram was recorded under above experimental conditions. An increase in wave height of the polarogram was observed without any change in half-wave potential, thus confirming the presence of Lindane in the sample. To standardise the polarographic procedure for the qualitative and quantitative analysis of the said pesticide, some

experimental sets with varying concentrations of Lindane were prepared and their polarograms were recorded, under experimental conditions discussed above.

The results indicated no change in $E_{1/2}$ value of the aforesaid pesticide. It was also observed that the concentration of Lindane is directly proportional to its wave height. Thus reconfirming the possibility of an accurate qualitative and quantitative determination of the said organochlorine pesticide in the sample.

Well defined polarogram is obtained for Lindane content in fruits and vegetables in each case with its $E_{1/2} = -0.995$ V vs SCE. Method of external spiking was used to ascertain the presence of Lindane in the extracted samples. On the basis of the observed polarographic data the concentration of Lindane (Table 1) in different fruits/vegetables is found as follows.

Lemon juice (68.54 $\mu\text{g/mL}$), grapes (384.46 $\mu\text{g/mL}$), banana (117.10 $\mu\text{g/mL}$), papaya (68.50 $\mu\text{g/mL}$), peanuts (200.36 $\mu\text{g/mL}$), carrot (373.40 $\mu\text{g/mL}$), tomato juice (329.50 $\mu\text{g/mL}$), blood sample (56 $\mu\text{g/mL}$), soft drinks-A (205.40 $\mu\text{g/mL}$), soft drinks-B (175.20 $\mu\text{g/mL}$).

In the above analysis percentage recovery was always above 99.6 and the standard deviation and coefficient of variance never exceeded 0.04 and 2.5 respectively. Thus confirming the reliability of the analysis.

The DC polarograms of Lindane content in soft drinks produced a reduced wave heights as compared to that observed with blank. The reduction in wave height in the

Table 1. Polarographic analysis of Lindane in natural origin, biological and industrial samples

Sl. no.	Sample	Added (mg)	Found (mg/ml)	%R	%S.D.	C.V.
1.	Lemon (5 ml)	-	0.79	99.41	0.40	1.14
		0.26	-			
2.	Peanuts (5 ml)	-	0.74	99.98	0.30	0.31
		0.26	-			
3.	Grapes (5 ml)	-	0.60	99.98	0.40	0.19
		1.32	-			
4.	Carrot (5 ml)	-	0.55	99.96	0.20	0.12
		1.32	-			
5.	Tomato (5 ml)	-	0.33	99.97	0.40	2.54
		1.32	-			
6.	Banana (3 ml)	-	0.09	99.85	0.04	0.11
		0.26	-			
7.	Papaya (5 ml)	-	0.08	99.62	0.21	0.63
		0.26	-			
8.	Soft drinks-A (20 ml)	-	3.02	99.98	0.04	0.01
		1.08	-			
9.	Soft drinks-B (20 ml)	-	3.14	99.9	0.04	0.10
		0.36	-			
10.	Blood (2 ml)	-	0.59	99.76	0.10	0.09
		0.52	-			
		-	1.12 mg/2 ml			

first sample solution may be explained on the basis of matrix effect. However, on further increase concentration in soft drinks resulted in proportionally increased wave heights. The results on the analysis of soft drinks, sample is depicted in Table 1. The table shows the presence of Lindane in soft drinks (A) 205 µg/mL and (B) 175 µg/mL.

Lindane in blood showed peculiar behaviour. Its presence in blood produced a reduced wave height as compared to that observed with blank. The reduction in wave height in the first sample solution may be explained on the basis of matrix effect. However, on further increase in concentration of Lindane in blood resulted in propor-

tionally increased wave heights.

The results on the analysis of human blood sample is depicted in Table 1. The table shows the presence of 56.0 mg/100 mL of Lindane in blood. Sample obtained from persons exposed to Lindane atmosphere i.e. in its manufacturing industry. Normally Lindane is absent in human blood but in some cases its presence is found positive due to uptake of edible things and in the sample of occupationally exposed persons.

Experimental

Apparatus : An (Elico, India) DC polarograph model CL-357, was used for polarographic study. The polaro-

Note

graphic cell consisted of three electrode assembly with a saturated calomel electrode (as reference electrode), a platinum electrode (as auxiliary electrode) and the working electrode was a dropping mercury electrode.

The pH measurements were made on a Systronics (India) digital pH-meter model-335. All the chemicals used were of reagent grade.

Extraction and analyte preparation for the analysis of Lindane in :

Fruits and vegetables : Fruits/vegetables (15 g of each) were cut into pieces and crushed well with the help of grinder. The crushed mass was dissolved in 20 ml acetone and the final volume made upto 40 ml with distilled water. The solution was allowed to stand for two hours, stirred and filtered. 5 ml of sample solution (filtrate) was mixed with 5 ml of (0.1 M) TMAB as supporting electrolyte. The final volume of analyte was made upto 50 ml with distilled water and the pH of the test solution was adjusted to 10 ± 0.2 with dil. NaOH/HCl solution.

Soft drinks : 20 ml of soft drink sample was mixed with (0.1 M) 5 ml of TMAB as supporting electrolyte. The final volume of analyte was made upto 50 ml with distilled water and pH of the test solution was adjusted to 10 ± 0.2 with dil. NaOH/HCl solution.

Blood : Blood sample was procured from Niramaya Pathology, Parkota, Sagar (M.P.). 0.2 ml blood sample was mixed with (0.1 M) 5 ml of TMAB as supporting electrolyte. The final volume of analyte was made upto 50 ml with distilled water and pH of the test solution was adjusted to 10 ± 0.2 with dil. NaOH/HCl solution. (1 ml blood contained 0.1 ml, 2% EDTA anticoagulant solution).

Preparation of analyte and recording of the polarograms :

Sample solution of Lindane (0.9 mM) was prepared in

acetone and water (3 : 2 v/v). Experimental set containing 5 ml of sample solution. 5 ml of TMAB (0.1 M) as supporting electrolyte was prepared. The final volume of test solution was made upto 50 ml with doubly distilled water. The pH of the test solution was adjusted to 10 ± 0.2 using dil. NaOH/HCl solution.

The analyte was placed in a polarographic cell equipped with the electrode assembly as described above. Pure nitrogen gas was passed through the test solution for 15 min at the beginning of the experiment. The polarogram was then recorded.

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